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OIKODOMOS

a virtual campus to promote the study of dwelling in contemporary Europe

WORKPACKAGE PR PROM

Report on Promotion

Authors: Jan Tucny, Stéphane Sadoux

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w o r k p a c k a g e	Report on Promotion
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authors	Jan Tucny, Stéphane Sadoux
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This document summarizes activities carried out as part of the PROM workpackage, and sets out a number of concrete outcomes and results. In particular, it highlights a number of actions undertaken with regards to the promotion of the project amongst the different target groups identified for the project.

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1. Introduction

The PROM workpackage is dedicated to raising awareness with regards to the issues and trends shaping contemporary forms of dwelling in Europe through different activities of the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus. It also seeks to widely disseminate and promote the objectives of the OIKODOMOS project itself, both from a pedagogic point of view, but also in terms of the information and communication technologies which have made it possible to implement the various workpackages.

1.1) Objectives

The aim of the workpackage is to promote the project amongst partners, academics, institutions, professionals, local authorities and citizens, to inform these various target audiences about the project implementation, the issues it addresses and its functionalities and to associate target audiences defined in the project application to the implementation of the project workpackages. It helps to test the ways in which it can be adapted to the various publics which would benefit from the training for architects, planners, elected members in the field of contemporary dwelling in Europe and its stakes.

1.2) Strategies

Four ways to promote the Virtual Campus have been selected and translated into specific or complementary actions :

- a. Raising awareness about the project and about the various databases and methods it has created (most notably the Case Repository, Workshops joint learning activities, digital Workspaces) amongst partners – universities, professionals and institutions.
- b. Enhancing the visibility of the European partnership formed for this project, by widening the exchange and collaboration network, and by enriching the ways in which housing projects are developed in architecture and planning.
- c. Allowing various target audiences (students, professionals, elected members and citizens) to be associated or trained through this project
- d. Demonstrating the « virtual » dimension of the tool by experimenting distance project work, with a multicultural team working on a synchronous/a-synchronous complementary basis.

The promotion builds upon existing products or examples. Because of the gradual implementation of the tools and contents of the Virtual Campus, initial promotion actions had to rely on the project rational and on the dissemination of the issues it addresses. In the first phase of project the PROM team used theHOUSING@21.EU database for communication, as well as the OIKODOMOS.org website and the various teaching experiments such as the Bratislava-Grenoble pilot Virtual Design Studio which aimed at further developing training methods.

As the OIKODOMOS project progressed, the PROM team was able to draw from additional material such as the participation of OIKODOMOS team members in various high profile conferences and the dissemination of the lessons learned from the various workshops that have been organized throughout the OIKODOMOS project and that have formed a major part of the overall programme.

1.3) Target groups

The promotion was oriented to inform or associate to the project five selected target audiences :

- Academics and partner university research groups
- Practitioners and their regional and national associations
- European and national associations of Schools of Planning and Architecture
- Local authorities
- Local citizen groups associated on the workshops and open-session presentations

2. Activities and approaches

To guarantee the best possible promotion of the programme and to be able to adapt information to each specific audience, PROM activities are tailored to the following channels: Academics, Professionals, Citizens and the media. The following list reports events and activities carried out during the OIKODOMOS project.

2.1) Academics

On the one hand, contact seminars were organized and held with local academic and research partners organized in order to establish links. On the other hand, similar links were made with teachers and education researchers, associations of schools of architecture and planning and on the other hand, higher education administration.

Activities promoted during the 2007/8 academic year, from the beginning of the programmed PROM workpackage to the end of June 2008, took the form of several meetings or demonstrating sessions of the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus aims, functionalities and on-going learning modules (pilot studio).

- a. EU Research seminar Grenoble IUG /PACTE-Territoire,(F) February 2008
 - An awareness campaign for the OIKODOMOS project was run with a showcase presentation of selected outcomes (access to the HOUSING@21.EU database produced by Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona and different ICT tools testing) during the international conference "4e Rencontres Internationales d'Urbanisme" organized by Grenoble University (Institute d'Urbanisme de Grenoble) on February 7th and 8th 2008. Attendance, approx. 200 French and European delegates.
 - A videoconference with Bratislava University was organized on February 8th, presenting ICT tools and the case study sites selected for the Pilot Virtual Design Studio Grenoble-Bratislava. Students from IUG and congress delegates attended this public workshop session. The videoconference was recorded and can be viewed in streaming format Real Player, on the Grenoble University video server. Address for connection: <rtsp://elvire.msh-alpes.fr/tice/upmf/iug/oiko1.rm>
- b. Accreditation by SRES 2007-2010 (F) (November 2007)
 - The IUG project "Ateliers Européens d'Urbanisme" (European Urban Planning Workshops) linked to the OIKODOMOS Virtual Design Studio was submitted for accreditation to the French regional scheme for higher education (Schéma Régional d'Enseignement Supérieur 2007-2010). The project has been accepted and the information on OIKODOMOS activities were sent to the representatives of Regional Council Rhône-Alpes.
- c. Interdisciplinary academic cooperation, widening OIKODOMOS network (since February 2008)
 - Contact with ENSAG (Grenoble School of Architecture) to organize possible cooperation around the « Ateliers européens d'Urbanisme » regional project, to use and promote OIKODOMOS and to examine a possible association of both schools and students in the common training programme. Local student teams integrating architects and urban planners were set up in some of the OIKODOMOS workshops.
 - Contacts with University of Lyon-Institut d'Urbanisme IUL have paved the way for a similar cooperation.
- d. Awareness raising campaign amongst academic milieu and partners: Symposium MOBAT (F) (10-11 June 2008)
 - Presentation of the OIKODOMOS Pilot Virtual Design Studio at the MOBAT Symposium "Sustainable building and environment" University of Grenoble Pierre Mendès-France, University Joseph Fourier, ADEME, Région Rhône-Alpes . 100 participants, academics, researchers, local authorities. Video presentation of students' distant project works for Bratislava urban housing development.

- e. Enhancement of the OIKODOMOS project visibility: Exhibitions at FA-STU (SK) et IUG (F) (May and June 2008, April 2009 and October-November 2009)
- Results from students' Virtual Design Studio (VDS) works were presented at a poster and video exhibition in May 2008 in Bratislava (Slovak Technical University FA-STU and Union of Slovak Architects SAS)
 - Another exhibition at Grenoble University-IUG in June-July 2008 and in 2009. VDS activities and results can be consulted on workshop website <http://webtek-02.upmf-grenoble.fr/> and OIKODOMOS website <http://www.oikodomos.org/>.
 - Contacts have been made with the Grenoble School of Architecture to hold an exhibition in the School Gallery which continuously hosts a wide range of architecture and design related events and exhibitions.
- f. OIKODOMOS workshops and VDS (May-July 2008)
- A common promotion action was launched to inform and advertise through flyers and websites about OIKODOMOS workshops for European students which started in October 2008 in Ghent. The flyer design and realisation was under Sint Lucas School of Architecture supervision. A similar publication was produced for workshops in Grenoble (F) and Bratislava (SK) in March and July 2009.
- g. Visibility of OIKODOMOS in the EU academic and research worlds:
- International Conference on the first international conference on "Online Repositories in Architecture" Venice, 20-21 Sept. 2008, organized by the EAAE (European Association for Architectural Education) and Collaboratorio (Italy) from the MACE project partnership (<http://www.mace-project.eu>). Presentation of the results of the evaluation of the HOUSING@21.EU, carried out within the workpackages PR EA 1 and PR EA 2.
 - Publication of the paper "Integrating learning spaces and architectural repositories" in the book of the MACE conference.
 - Publication of articles on OIKODOMOS learning activities in the Slovakian review " Informacie, Architektura, Interier, Design" , Yudiny, November 2008
- h. Partners from IUG, FASTU-Bratislava and URL have been particularly active in disseminating the objectives of the project among colleagues at their respective Schools, in order to gain the support of faculty and students to the project's activities, particularly with those related with the implementation of the learning programme.

Promotion activities amongst academic and/or teaching and training networks were pursued during the 2008/9 and 2009/10 academic years

j. The contacts established between IUG and the Grenoble School of Architecture were successfully pursued, as architecture students joined urban planning students for the Grenoble and Bratislava workshops. This was unique opportunity to foster cross departmental links in a concrete and pedagogically-driven manner, and was also a useful occasion to promote the project amongst students and staff of the school of architecture [1000 students and 150 teachers]. It should be stated that architect Claude Vasconi, who champions the major project for the site used as a basis for the Grenoble workshop, gave a major conference about his work and more specifically about this particular project (GIANT) This conference was attended by all IUG students involved in the project in order for them to feed information into the workshop. The conference is available in streaming format on website (www.grenoble.archi.fr)

k. An article « ERASMUS 2.0. Oikodomos » about the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus project was published in the Grenoble University newsletter « Intercours » (N° 568, April 2009), with an interview of Prof. Dr. Jan Tucny who gave an overview of the many benefits of a cross disciplinary, cross cultural and European approach to a project such as OIKODOMOS. The presentation of the « Virtual » and « real » workshop Housing for Diversity, organized by IUG with partners schools students and teachers invited academics and French students to discover the function that European workshop could play in innovative learning programmes and in local debates on urban housing development strategies for the Grenoble-Giant district.

l. IUG participated in a conference and workshop held in Paris (1-2 July 2009) about creativity and innovation organized by the French Ministry of National Education and by Europe Education Formation France. These events showcased and allowed to discuss forty higher education and training projects that were selected. For a full description of the event, please refer to www.2e2f.fr.

m. IUG presented its aims, objectives and achievements at an international conference held in Lyon, France, on November 19th 2009 ["Apport des projets européens d'éducation et de formation tout au long de la vie"] and organized by the French agency *Europe-Education-Formation 2 E 2F*. The OIKODOMOS project was selected in the framework of the EU Year of Creativity and Innovation amongst the six best projects supported by the ERASMUS, LEONARDO, GRUNTVIG, COMENIUS, ERASMUS-MUNDUS, and TEMPUS European programmes.

n. A final Conference « In Conclusion – The Final Workshop » was organized by URL in Barcelona on December 10th and 11th 2009. It brought together the various project partners and other academic audiences to present the project method, the innovative workspaces generated through the project, as well as the collaborative teaching and learning activities. A discussion forum focused on the collaborative use and development of tailored online environments was introduced by keynote speakers - Prof. Hillary French (Royal College of Art in London) and Prof. Lorenzo Cantoni (Universita della Svizzera Italiana, Lugano).

o. The OIKODOMOS project will be presented at the forthcoming INTED2010 conference [« International Technology, Education and Development »]. The event is scheduled to take place in Valencia, from 8th to 10th of March.

2.2) Practitioners and their regional and national associations

Public awareness campaigns have been organized with regional and national associations of practitioners. Information focused on the professional target audiences (architects, urban planners, developers...) prepared the association of these partners in the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus project, as participants on teaching tasks (tutors in workshops, consultants for student work assessments, lecturers for specific professional modules...) or as lifelong learners trained through this project.

- a. Awareness raising about the OIKODOMOS project and partnership: professional associations meeting Lyon (F) (January 2008)
 - Contacts with representatives from French professional associations and unions (SFU-Société Française des Urbanistes, CFDU – Conseil Français des Urbanistes, ARU) to disseminate information about the possibilities offered through the OIKODOMOS project and to associate professionals to the OIKODOMOS Pilot Workshop. Meeting with the ARU (Association Régionale des Urbanistes), SFU, CERTU–Centre Européen de Recherches Techniques et Urbanisme, January 8th 2008 in Lyon (presentation of OIKODOMOS project.)
- b. Participation on the OIKODOMOS project: (F) (February – April 2008), ARU Lyon, New Towns, Nantes
 - Contacts have been established with the regional board of French planners and architects (regional association ARU Rhône-Alpes/Auvergne) in order to associate them to the project. In a first phase they were integrated as teachers/tutors or consultants for Virtual Design Studios and in a second phase, starting in 2009, as end-users in the framework of lifelong learning protocol. Contents of specific short courses for continuing professional development are currently discussed with ARU executive board.
 - Two members of the regional association of practitioners ARU and representatives of New Town Isle d'Abeau local authorities have been associated to the management of the Pilot Virtual Design Studio Grenoble-Bratislava in March-April 2008 as tutors for students' groupworks.
 - Meeting with Direction du Développement Urbain and Direction des Projets Internationaux in Nantes Métropole on March 19th 2008. Nantes demonstrates the relevance and interest of tools like OIKODOMOS in the development of European projects. Nantes Metropole, involved in the EU projects Urban-“Housing for all” and EU Atlantic Arc cooperation wishes to be kept up to date with the OIKODOMOS' development and with the functionalities of distance learning.

- c. Awareness about OIKODOMOS project and network : SAS Bratislava (SK) (June 2008)
 - An exhibition of students' Virtual Design Studio works has been proposed to the Slovak Union of Architects SAS to be installed in the SAS exhibition area in their historical palace in the city centre of Bratislava. First contacts taken at this moment will prepare the further possible involvement of practitioners in the learning activities.
- d. Summer School 'CFDU Paris-Créteil' (F) (27-29 August 2008)
 - The OIKODOMOS project and results of Pilot Virtual Design Studio have been presented to the 13th annual Summer University CFDU (Conseil Français des Urbanistes – French Council of Urban Planners, member of European Council of Town Planners). A series of conferences about Development, fragmentation and cohesion of metropolitan areas included professional sessions and forums on sustainable eco-housing, research and innovative professional training. In cooperation with Regional Association of Planners ARU, Information about the OIKODOMOS project and programmed activities (workshops) has been disseminated on these forums. Approximately 300 participants attended this national and European event. Further cooperation with CFDU and ARU are expected for the next series of OIKODOMOS workshops.
- e. Contacts with national associations of architects and planners (E, CH, SK,B)
 - After the first identification of relevant professional partners by OIKODOMOS project partners in Spain, Switzerland and Slovakia, contacts with national or regional Chambers of Architects will be taken in order to disseminate information about the project issues and opportunities and organize the participation of practitioners on some forthcoming activities (Design Studio workshops, students' work assessment, short lifelong learning modules selection and implementation.). In Spain, URL has maintained contacts with the Chamber of Catalan Architects, in Barcelona, who have given their support to promote programme's activities through their communication channels. Discussions with professionals in Belgium helped to organize the OIKODOMOS workshop on Flexible Housing in Ghent (October 2008).
 - Further cooperation with CFDU and ARU was established for the "Housing for Diversity" OIKODOMOS workshop, held in Grenoble in April 2009. Practitioners from Grenoble (3), from Rhône-Alpes region (2) and from Paris (1) were involved directly on the students' groupwork preparation or in the project studio supervision and online evaluation of deliverables.
 - Contacts established in 2009 with SFU (Société Française des Urbanistes) will be maintained following the completion of the OIKODOMOS Project in order to define possible adaptations of the Virtual Campus experience to the design of a tool for lifelong learning targeted towards planning professionals, but also to their involvement in tutoring for workshops. The president of SFU J.-P. Gautry will personally keep track of this collaboration.
 - Results from Virtual Campus activities and the topic of Contemporary dwelling in Europe were presented in the Slovak professional reviews ARCH and Forum Architektury, in November 2009.

2.3) European and national associations of Schools of Planning and Architecture

Information campaigns with this target group enhance the visibility of the European academic partnership, by widening the exchange and collaboration network. Exchange of experience and best practice with national or European associations also helps to obtain valuable supports and evaluations for accreditation processes necessary in the next "consolidation" phase of the project.

- a. AESOP teaching programme contest (EU, USA) (April-July 2008)
 - Presentation of the issues covered in the OIKODOMOS project to the AESOP (Association of European Schools of Planning) Teaching programme commission in order to submit the Virtual Pilot Design Studio for the "Best teaching programme" selection and spread information about the project at the joint AESOP-ACSP international congress in Chicago in July 2008..
 - The OIKODOMOS project was then mentioned in the AESOP newsletter, published on the internet and read by hundreds of academics involved in various fields related to urban planning, design, environmental design, architecture etc.
 - A special information about the OIKODOMOS Final Conference in Barcelona was sent to all 120 AESOP Member schools in November and December 2009.

- b. EADTU Conference Paris (F) (September 2008)
 - Preparation of a contribution about the distant workshop (Pilot Design Studio OIKODOMOS) for the 2008 EADTU conference « Lifelong open and flexible learning in higher education – networked teaching and learning », hosted under French EU Presidency in Paris (September 2008)
- c. APERAU France-Europe (2008, 2009)
 - The association of the French Schools of Urban Planning APERAU and its European members have been informed about the OIKODOMOS project and its pedagogical issues. APERAU was associated in the organization of the second Design Studio Workshop held in Grenoble in March 2009.
 - During the 13th Summer University CFDU in Paris-Créteil (September 2008), IUG, Regional association of professionals and APERAU Europe presented the OIKODOMOS project on the forum on innovative academic and professional training.
- d. Contacts with EAEE and ECAADE associations
 - Belgian colleagues from Sint-Lucas school are currently establishing contacts with the network of European schools of architecture.

2.4) Local authorities

Local authorities are associated to the OIKODOMOS project activities under the similar way as professionals, architects and urban planners. During the first phase of project, two municipalities participated in the workshop themes and sites selection, groupwork tutoring and final project assessments.

- a. Workshop themes selection Bratislava (SK) (February 2008)
 - Selection of three case study areas for Pilot Virtual Design Studio in cooperation with FA-STU and Mayor office Bratislava
- b. Student's project tutoring Grenoble Pilot VDS (F) (March-April 2008)
 - Two members of New Town Isle d'Abeau Municipality participated on the students' groupwork projects as tutors and advisors.
- c. Workshop open sessions with non-academic partners ,Bratislava (SK) (May 2008) and Grenoble (F) (June 2008)
 - Show-case presentation of OIKODOMOS programme and Pilot Virtual Design Studio groupwork projects analyzed with representatives of Bratislava Mayor Office and French local authorities delegates on MOBAT Symposium
- d. Workshop Grenoble (April 2009)
 - The links established with the local authority in Grenoble were maintained and strengthened for the organization and promotion of the Grenoble workshop. Several local and national authorities representatives took part in the workshop activities (presentation of the site and local policies, lectures, urban & housing studios supervision, evaluation, online assessments, member of the jury in the final student presentations. ...)
(Deputy Mayor P. de Longevialle, P. Kermen, member of the Grenoble Local council, Mrs G.Fioraso, Membre of Parliament in charge of GIANT area development, representatives of Local developers, Mr L.Gaillard, Head of Grenoble Urban Development Office, Y.Goetz, City of Echirolles Urban Planner, J.J. Faure President of regional association of Planners...)

2.5) Citizens

OIKODOMOS project invites citizen groups to exchange information and experience about local projects of housing and urban development with students and academics. Project team asks also for eventual propositions of practical problems concerning local context to be treated by OIKODOMOS case studies or workshops.

1. Open meetings and exhibitions

- Workshops in partner schools were an opportunity to display projects and posters from students groupwork in public spaces, university halls, (Ghent: October 2008, Grenoble: May-June 2008, April 2009, October-November 2009, Bratislava: April 2008, October 2009), and in municipality exhibition areas (Bratislava-Dubravka October 2009) and contacted local media to inform larger public (Bratislava, Grenoble).

Essentially for linguistic reasons, because of the major part of communication and information remains in English, this relationship failed. We consider for the future a necessary enhancement of the national languages versions or bi-lingual versions of some project activities – even perhaps special events in French in French, Slovak or Dutch for example - only at the beginning of projects so as to make sure that the target audiences are not left out from an early stage.

2.6) Media

OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus, Pilot Design Studio, digital workspaces and the case study repository were promoted via several media and public information channels.

- Interviews of OIKODOMOS teaching staff and students participating on the Grenoble-Bratislava Virtual Design Studio
- Slovak Radio SR2 Regina(21 May 2008) (accessible on http://ra.slovakradio.sk:8000/file/www/portal/sound_52000.mp3)
- Article on OIKODOMOS projects for Bratislava (A. Bednarova, J. Tucny, Journal Informacie Design, Architektura, Bratislava), July 2008 , accessible sur <http://www.yudiny.sk>
- Interviews of OIKODOMOS team participating on Management meeting in Bratislava (11 July 2008) by Slovak Radio SR2
- Newsletters OIKODOMOS, displayed on the project website (www.oikodomos.org) and on partner school websites (www.iug-grenoble.fr, www.stuba.sk, www.salle.url.edu, www.architectuur.sintlucas.wenk.be, where also specific articles, reports, students projects and news from OIKODOMOS are presented.
- Several lectures and/or videoconferences and distant groupworks were recorded in video and accessible from university websites via internet streaming systems . (Example of introduction to the Pilot studio Grenoble-Bratislava, lectures at Grenoble and Bratislava workshops, Final Conference Barcelona.) Some of these documents are filtered by logins, because of the national and EU regulations on copyrights.
- As was the case in Bratislava, where local and national media visited the organising institutions during the event, the Grenoble workshop was the occasion to promote the project throughout the local media. A journalist from the local/regional daily newspaper « Le Dauphiné Libéré » was invited to the event and joined other participants to gain a better understanding of the aims and objectives of the workshop. This generated an article in the newspaper.

3. Outcomes

The OIKODOMOS team produced in 2008 different events, and information supports:

- Contact seminars and project presentation with local academic and research partners
- Public awareness campaigns with regional and national associations of practitioners,
- Test of Local Authorities participation on student's virtual design studios and workshops
- Exchange of experience and best practice with colleagues from European Schools networks
- Exhibitions of students' works produced in the framework of OIKODOMOS Pilot Design studio
- Presentation of the Virtual Campus and students' projects in local media (interviews radio, articles press, video)
- Presentation of project's outcomes at international conferences (MACE, September 2008)

4. Conclusion

It is paramount that the outcomes of the project, both in pedagogic and network building terms, are further strengthened and fed into forthcoming teaching, research and promotion activities of each of the OIKODOMOS project partners. The considerable student groupwork productions that have come out of the workshops, as well as the generous publicizing of these events through various channels, offer a unique canvas to gain in efficiency in forthcoming collaborations.

However, and as noted above, a number of obstacles should be addressed with regards to the promotional dimension of these various activities and outputs. The language barrier, which, it is true, is more or less of a handicap depending on the country, has been a considerable burden when trying to establish *sustainable* contacts with local and national target groups – a situation which is particularly true in France where, by law (Loi Toubon), all major conferences in the academic field should be given in French as well as the foreign language of the speaker. We noticed similar constraints and obstacles in Slovakia, where the use of English is more proficient in academic milieu than in the communication with citizens. This implies that the national adaptation may be a fruitful complement to the "European" core of the virtual Campus contents and activities. But considerable investments in terms of finances and time to allow such set ups to be implemented. However, at this time, offering translation is sadly the only possible way of reaching out to those target audiences which the project sought to include (most importantly local decision makers, technicians and politicians) for them to take part in the project as tutors, facilitators, or simply for giving conferences aimed at providing students with substantial input for the groupwork.